

REGISTER OF RE-ENACTING THE IGBO ANCESTRAL SIGNIFICANCE IN *ORIMILI*: AN ACCOUNT OF ORIMILI'S STRUGGLE FOR ACCEPTANCE IN OKOCHA

Abstract

Register, according to linguists, is a variety of a language used for a particular purpose or in a particular setting that provides a link between a communicative act and the context of situation in which it occurs. Using Halliday's theory of register (1989), the study observed a number of registers that re-enact Igbo ancestral significance and examined the linguistic forms and meanings of the selected registers as used in Amechi Akwanya's novel, *Olimiri*. The three register elements (field, tenor, and mode) were used to project cultural variations and context of situation projected in the text. The findings in the study show that the field of discourse reveals the nature of the social actions being carried out as well as the topic of the social activities in that Igbo society. The social-role relationship described by the tenor of discourse projects a high level of affective involvement between the reader and the author while the written mode of discourse is significant for re-enacting the Igbo cultural peculiarities in the mind of the readers.

Introduction

Register, according to linguists, is a variety of a language used for a particular purpose or in a particular setting that provides a link between a communicative act and the context of situation in which it occurs (Van Thao, 2020). The term was first used by Thomas Bertram Reid in 1956 and was made famous by a group of linguists in the 1960s. A language variety assessed in the light of its usage and language variants connected to situational types have generally been referred to by terms such as register, genre, text types, and styles. These terms are very different from dialect which is used to describe linguistic variants connected to specific user groups such as those marked by geographic region, educational attainment, social status, sex, etc. This concept of register is essentially central to the Halliday's model of language and it holds all the dimensions of the systemic functional linguistics together (Lukin et al, 2011). Halliday's language model

demonstrates how open language is to the eco-social environment and, consequently, to the dynamics of social development. Halliday's concept of register is well suited particularly to describing language consistency and variation without equating that variation with the social variation.

The idea of register, which is part of the framework of systemic functional linguistics, postulates a very close correlation between contextual elements and the linguistic components of a text. This is represented in the three variables of register: field, tenor, and mode. These factors govern the system of language choices identified in Halliday's three regions of meaning namely ideational, interpersonal and textual.

The Igbo culture is substantially the Igbo's lifestyle, custom, idea, and social conduits for the preservation of the Igbo cultural heritage. These could be in the form of books, scripts, articles or any piece of writing at all on the Igbo heritage and cultural behavior. The present study has investigated the register of re-enacting the Igbo ancestral significance in Amechi Akwanya's *Orimili* using Halliday's theory of register.

Literature Review

Moulita (2021) investigated the content words and noun phrases of the English register and their meanings as employed in The Jakarta Post's Football news. The study obtained its data from the Jakarta Post Football news and used documentation as the instrument. The model proposed by Elo and Kyangas (2007) were used to analyze the data and it was found that the content words comprises of eight nouns and two verbs. All English registers found in The Jakarta Post's football news have different meanings when compared with their conceptual meaning in the dictionary. Thus, for the researcher, the most overt type of change in meaning is social meaning.

Jeffery (2002) examined the theory of register-analysis as a means of eliciting meanings from literary texts. This study proposed the concept of register as a meaning-potential. Register is seen as meaning a determinants caused by situation type, which can be precisely defined by means of categories of (discourse-) situation. Five of such categories are put forward. Their application constituted register-analysis. The process is demonstrated on a literary text, and it is claimed that an intuitive, practical-criticism-type analysis could not be as clear, precise and comprehensive as a register-analysis. And the coherent theory of meaning which supplies the

categories also provides a consistent, defined meta language to work in. So register-analysis offers a significant advance on intuitive reading.

Nguyen et al (2020) investigated the application of Halliday's register model to language majored students' translation assessment at a university in Vietnam, specifically at Faculty of Foreign Languages of Nha Trang University. The study examined the difference between two selected groups of students and conducted a survey on students' TQA activity. The purposes of this survey are to see how the students carry out peer assessment activity and to measure to what extent the TQA activity also affects students' translation competence. The data collected for the study was an instructed TQA criterion which is introduced to one of the groups. The results of this research show the benefits of constructed criteria for TQA in learning and teaching translation at tertiary level.

Research Methods

This study is a content analysis which is a research method that uses qualitative or quantitative data to analyze written data (such as a document, book, magazine, etc.) and verbal or visual communication messages to provide knowledge and a deep understanding of the data. The information was presented in a descriptive manner by describing the phenomenon of register usage. This study's final report is a narrative rather than a statistical analysis. The information was gathered from Amechi Akwanya's prose text *Orimili*. The research data consists of sentences that contain the register words and phrases used in *Orimili* which was published in 1991. Finding, organizing, and reconstructing the writer's story yields the data.

Theoretical Framework

The Systemic Functional Linguistic

The Systemic Functional Linguistic was developed around the mid 20th century and is one of the Functional linguistic approaches. Having first being developed by M.A.K. Halliday, as an extension of the Firth's linguistics, it is pre-dated by the Prague School functionalism. The Systemic Functional Linguistic is a holistic theory of language that theorizes language as a higher-order semiotic system within a semiotic system. The Systemic Functional Linguistic is a

component of the semiotic complex of language in context and this is absolutely crucial because any approach to register must include an account of context which is the meaning potential in language (e.g., Halliday 1973).

The concept of register in the context of systemic functional linguistics proposes a very close correlation between contextual elements and linguistic components of a text. This is because the three register elements (field, tenor, and mode) govern the language system's options in the three regions of meaning identified by Halliday (ideational, interpersonal and textual).

Halliday's Theory of Register

The complete framework for the characterization of context is register analysis. This is because it establishes a crucial connecting line between a communicative act and the situational context in which it takes place. Register is said to be the arrangement of semantic resources that a member of a culture usually connects to a certain circumstance/situation type. It is the meaning capacity that is available in a specific social setting. This is well supported by Halliday (1978:111) when he defined register as;

the configuration of semantic resources that the member of a culture typically associates with a situation type. It is the meaning potential that is accessible in a given social context. Both the situation and the register associated with it can be described by varying degrees of specificity; but the existence of registers is a fact of everyday experience – speakers have no difficulty in recognizing semantic options and combinations of options that are “at risk” under particular environmental conditions. Since these options are realized in the form of grammar and vocabulary, the register is recognizable as a particular selection of words and structures. But it is defined in terms of meanings; it is not an aggregate of conventional forms of expression superposed on some underlying content by “social factors” of one kind or another. It is the selection of meanings that constitutes the variety to which a text belongs.

Holmes (2001) defines register as the language of a group of people with common interests or jobs; or the language used in situations associated with such groups. The term register is

described as the language of groups of people with common interest or jobs or used in situations associated with such groups. In short, we can define register as a language used for a particular purpose or in a particular social setting. The kind of confinement that context imposes on text is very clear. It predicts textual elements from a given contextual configuration and infers context from the text. Thus, the text is compared to a mirror than a window in that it reflects meaning back at the reader. Since context is integrated into text, the linguistic choices made at the ideational, interpersonal, and textual levels of meaning are all governed by a particular configuration of field, tenor, and mode, respectively and they leave their traces in the text. Furthermore, particular lexico-grammatical structures also help to actualize meanings.

Field, tenor and mode are the three variables of register and they determine writer's choices from a linguistic system. These three variables construct the register and determine meaning diversity within the different context of use in any discourse.

The Field of discourse describes the topics or activities which readers engage and the nature of the social action being carried out. This expresses the ideational metafunction. It particularly answers the questions "What is going on around the discourse? What kind of activity is the discourse situated in? How does discourse relate to the domain and the topics of discourse?" (Jeffery, 2002) The domain of a literary text may comprise on the one hand title, author, date, genre, relationship to other texts in the same genre, and to other works by the same author (Wales, 2001c). The Field of discourse also discusses how language represents social experiences, activities and understanding of the world. According to Moulit (2021) linguistic forms in this category could be realized via word classes such as nouns, verbs and adjectives or grammatical categories such as clauses, sentences. Halliday (2014) explains field as the goals of a given situation, an intended outcome, and more specifically an "expounding" context where the speaker's goal might be to construe taxonomy for a classification of some classes of phenomena. Therefore, through these language categories, variation in language can be organized in terms of field or in terms of the classes of taxonomy.

The Tenor of Discourse exemplifies social role relationships expressed by the interactants. It is more specifically concerned with the relationship between the speakers, whether the speakers try to bring their addressees closer to their own positions or farther from their own positions. The relationship between participants in a social interaction can be defined along the three variables ,

namely; Power whether equal or unequal, the degree of accessibility or familiarity whether frequent or occasional and lastly, the level of affective involvement whether high or low. The Tenor of Discourse can be expressed through the interpersonal metafunction.

The Mode of Discourse according to Halliday (2014) is the role language and other semiotic systems play in the interaction. The division of labor between linguistic activities and other semiotic activities is determined by the mode of discourse. This category of discourse can also be measured along the variables of visual and aural contact as well as the feedback possibilities for a spatial/interpersonal/ experiential distance between participants. Ultimately, it calculates the distance between language and the social process occurring in terms of whether language accompanies the social process or constitutes it. The Mode of Discourse can also be written or spoken and could take a phonic or a graphic channel to communicate its message.

The importance of context to the interpretation of literary text

Texts are not just instantiations of registers rather they are a dynamic phenomenon that supports several registers. According to Halliday (1987), a text is a semantic unit, not always the end of the distinct physical object known as "a text"; it could consist of so many texts and has potentials for meanings based on situation types. Written texts are inescapably the main element of situations and, thus, the main source of information that determines meaning. Hence, literary works which are also a type of written texts include an information density that is atypical of the ordinary everyday writing. Therefore cooperation is often between a reader and a text for meaning to be produced from the information provided in the text. Readers provide some of the text's most important information as they collaboratively and actively build meaning with the author into the text rather than passively consuming it.

Literary writings first construct their own internal context in order to be understood, even though they are not hindered by the exterior circumstances or situation. Hence, literary writings are said to be enmeshed into two contextual fixtures: the outward context of situation, in which communication occurs between two real-world actors; the author and the reader, and the inward context of situation, in which the communicative act's participants are fictional. According to Halliday (1985), there are some text types, literary writing is an obvious example, where there is only the exterior context of situation for the reader. In such texts, readers must completely

construct the inner context from the reading of the text and since there is no particular context preceding the language of the text, the inner context often serves the role of an interpretative hypothesis when analyzing such a text. There is no one-to-one correspondence between a particular text and a particular register neither is there such a thing as literary register; instead literary texts are only prized for their originality and that is why they are only being regarded as containing a register for any class membership they may include. Our choice of the suitable interpretation for a text is often based on how we see the situation type. The text cannot exist alone; it is always a product of a circumstance/situation from which we must abstract in order to understand or uncover the meaning of the text. The potential meaning of that text depends on the situation type.

THE IGBO CULTURAL SIGNIFICANCE

The Igbo culture is substantially the culture, customs, ideas, and social behavior of the Igbo people of Eastern Nigeria. It is enmeshed in their way of living and their continuous relationships with other people. The arts, the literature and the Igbo-oriented theatrical performances are major ways of preserving the Igbo continuum. Within the Igbo culture lies its meaning and its life. Nwaru (2015) opines that the core of a man's being is culture. The Igbo expression "Omenala" naturally translates to the English term for culture and would obviously include the arts, artifacts, craft, poetry, music, beliefs, occupation, tales etc. The term Igbo culture could therefore be defined as a pattern that has been adopted by the Igbo society as a traditional way of solving its community's challenges.

The South East of Nigeria is a settlement for most Igbos apart from a major constituent in the diasporas; hence, the need for preservation of Igbo's cultural inheritance and its re-enactment. These cultural emblems, events, and arts are symbolic and can only be appreciated when they are made known to the upcoming generation. The Igbo people naturally glorify and cherish the beauty and usefulness of their arts, hence the need to have it entrenched in their philosophy and invariably enforcing a sense of identity even on members of the cultural group located in the diaspora.

Ikedi (2005) expresses that literary arts are conduits for the preservation of Igbo cultural heritage. These could be in the form of books, scripts, articles or any piece of writing at all on Igbo heritage and culture that could be used to document past events, and major legacies for the purpose of teaching young ones their history, religion, environment, customs, norms and values of society. Igbo representations and symbols such as title emblems, ritual ceremony, symbolic edibles and sounds are often painted in literature to reflect Igbo significance.

AmechiAkwanya's *Orimili* serves the role of re-enacting Igbo significance and promotion of Igbo cultural heritage through the plot expressing a journey of the protagonist's struggle for identity and acceptance in Okocha. The political title which ranks the highest in the village's governing structure seems to be worshipped in the prose and the esoteric nature of its rites builds in readers a sense of re-enactment of Igbo cultural significance.

DATA ANALYSIS

This research deals with the registers used in AmechiAkwanya's *Orimili*. This chapter presents the analyses of linguistic forms and meanings of English register used in the book. The forms and meanings of the selected registers will be discussed in details in this chapter. According to Halliday and Hasan (1989), the interaction between languages and the features of contexts is the context of a situation. The context is both situational and cultural and this exists in the discourse by influencing the linguistic variables employed by discourse producer. This study demonstrates some components such as contextual characteristics in registers, situational characteristics in registers, functional characteristics, and the significance of these characteristics within the register. These components mark the context of usage, and their linguistic features are unique to specific registers discussed. Halliday's three parameters such as the field of discourse, the mode of discourse and the tenor of discourse were used for the register analysis. The register items were categorized into linguistic categories that project Igbo cultural significance such as the names of characters, ritual ceremonies, status symbols, symbolic edibles and symbolic festivals and ceremony. Each of these linguistic categories presents a number of register items found within the context of situation in Amechi Akwanya's *Orimili* prose text.

Description of table: This study takes its source of data from strings of sentences weaved around the plot of Amechi Akwanya's *Orimili*. The language registers are presented in the form of words in the table but sentences and clauses that contain them were extracted from the text for a register analysis.

Table 1.1 REGISTER ITEMS

LINGUISTIC CATEGORIES OF IGBO CULTURAL SIGNIFICANCE	REGISTER ITEMS FOUND IN Amechi Akwanya's <i>Orimili</i>
1) Titles and Names of characters	Ekwenze Orimili, Ogbuefi,
2) Ritual ceremony	White, traditional chalk
3) Status symbols	The Ozo Society, Ozo title, Red barrette cap, Eagle feather, Okike, Ogilisi, Agbori, Echiiechi
4) Symbolic edibles	Kolanut and Aligator pepper
5) Symbolic festivals and ceremonies	Ozorite, Ozo feasts, Afor, Masquerading.

Table 1.1 presents a linguistic category of the register items of Igbo cultural significance found in the Amechi Akwanya's *Orimili*

1) Titles and Names

“*Orimili* had and held the idea long enough that the title was a most worthy and compelling goal to aspire to, had so often imagine himself decked out in the robes and emblems of Ozo and felt how becoming they were that he had begun to unconsciously associate to the title with himself.” (pg, 37)

“*Orimili* was a sensitive man. He took things a great deal to heart especially things that didn’t concern him personally. He took them to heart because they touched off a chord in his own mind and caused some vague fear to stir up and give him hell, before subsiding again to resume its vague form at the back of his mind.” (pg, 15)

Orimili’s background was obscure” (pg, 37)

“A seer had found out that the young *Ekwenze* was cheating his parents, for he secretly belonged to a company of river elemental had reincarnated a number of times into his parents’ anguished home, and preparing for yet another round of death and return, when he was found out by the powerful seer.” (pg, 94)

“*Ekwenze* grew up to love the river. As he grew older, and the ferry business prospered, he came to be known by the nickname ‘*Orimili*’, which was the local name of the river” (pg, 95)

“Because of this difference in outlook between *Orimili* and the great river, he answered to the name quite straightforwardly as a man might answer his surname, if his friends prefer to address him that way. He was the offspring of the god of the river, being a river-spirit as the seer had divined, and formerly part of the retinue of the river god.” (pg, 96)

The name *Orimili* exists within the domain of the prose text discourse which in this case spells the social setting of the story line and the field of discourse. *Orimili*, the protagonist of the text gives the prose discourse its significance. Every strands of the activity with the physical setting of the fiction in Okocha is consciously weaved around the personality and peculiarities of the protagonist, *Orimili*. The name of the protagonist is a nominal item that registers significance in the text and first of all, reminding us of the ancestral belief of reincarnation within the Igbo community. *Orimili* takes its name from a great river that flow through the town of Okocha where he lives and prospered. His affluence and desire to be integrated into the social structures

and ranks of kinship in Okocha fueled his passion for taking the Ozo title which is the object of his affection. He desires to secure his object of affection in two unique ways; one, taking a unique membership position of the Ozo ruling council in Okocha town and two, processing an arranged marriage between his son, Osita and Ogbuefi Emeneoha's daughter, Adaoba, who is an established townsman. In all his elaborate involvements and sacrifices, Orimili fell short in both attempt and became an object of controversy for all those involved in determining his lot. In all, his inability to trace his ancestral pedigree had hunted him and made his acceptance into the Okocha clan unattainable. The mode of the prose discourse expresses textual meaning through an unwritten channel and the degree of participation between the author and the reader is complex as the author addresses various intentions, thoughts and actions of the protagonist through the stream of consciousness. For the tenor of the discourse, the voice remains the same throughout, and is evidently meant to be taken as the author's. Nevertheless there is occasion to distinguish the voice from authors. The voice is identified as a third person point of view with overt acknowledgement of an audience. A name such as that of *Orimili* was given as a reflective of his personal ordeals which seem to anchor every other situational experience in the text. It also serves the chief role of creating curiosity in the mind of readers and a higher level of affectiveness while a reader reads. The name, therefore, serves a reflective purpose. This simply seems to be a deliberate act by the author. The implication of the name thus, reinforces the impression and beauty of tracing and knowing a man's ancestral identity beyond the prose text.

2) Status symbols, Ritual ceremony and Symbolic edibles

“Orimili had held the idea long enough that the title was a most worthy and compelling goal to aspire to and had so often imagined himself decked out in the robes and emblems of *Ozo* and felt how becoming they were that he had begun unconsciously to associate the title with himself “ (pg, 7)

“The one investment Edoko had made, which was still valuable, was his *Ozo title*.” (pg, 64)

“How could one value a boon which one succeeded into without paying a price? It was also reasonable that the successor should make a cash payment to the society; otherwise it wouldn't

be succession anymore but a fresh title. A live bull and a grand fete were not too much, even though... Now how was he going to find the money for a bull and the *Ozo feast*?" (pg, 64)

"As we all know having the firm purpose and the means to secure one a place in the *ozo society* is only one-half of the requirements. The individual must be of a good character. ... Is not the vulture a figure of the man of title in as much as both the baby bird and the mother look equally elderly? Aren't they all bald? An *ozo* is before other things an elder, be he young or old. That is why a candidate should be thoroughly examined for fitness; the younger the candidate the more thorough the scrutiny." (pg, 73)

"Do you know of any place in the igbo cultural where strangers are given the *Ozo title*? Every one of you is afraid of speaking the plain truth and that is why you are trying to lead the *Ozo society* of Okocha into an abomination." (pg, 77)

The domain of the above discourse register found in the prose text *Orimili* is the Igbo symbols and they were used symbolically in the text to pass across certain information that readers can relate with as regarding the cultural priorities of Igbo land. The *Ozo* title is Orimili's object of affection and pursuit in the text: "... so often imagined himself decked out in the robes and emblems of *Ozo* and felt how becoming they were that he had begun unconsciously to associate the title with himself". The society is one that projects dignity and fame in the community of Okocha and by extension in Igbo land since the prose text is reflective of the existing culture of Igbo land.

It takes so much to be a part of the *Ozo* society and that is because becoming a title holder in Igbo land is exclusively reserved for men of integrity and honor "As we all know having the firm purpose and the means to secure one a place in the *ozo society* is only one-half of the requirements. The individual must be of a good character...". The requirement for succeeding one who bore the title took a fortune talk more of one who would take a fresh title. As described in the text, the *Ozo* were in charge of Okocha community and decides what happens within their territory. In one of the scenes presented, the *Ozo* determined the lot of one man who had a glitch with masquerades; they also determined judgments on land disputes. When one finally succeeds in being a part of this society, the *Ozo* feast is celebrated; the network of kinship must be present and would rally round with provision of raw food for celebration.

The chalk cake feet are a mystic ritual ceremony that is associated with the Ozo title and it depicts openness and purity of the bearer. As a sign that the Ozo title of his father has been redeemed, this traditional chalk was placed on Mr Nduka's feet and this therefore signifies his incorporation into the Ozo society. The written mode of the discourse gives readers access to understand the peculiarity of the titled positions of Igbo land and opens them up to complex analysis with various addressee-involving linguistic mechanisms that characterizes the text. The chosen subset of register projects a third person point of view as in other parts of the prose text. The colloquial expressions and syntax of Igbo lexico semantic selections from the novel are simply a deliberate attempt by the author to create an informal Igbo setting as well as connect readers with cultural variables that are not eccentric to members of that tribe. Therefore, readers can study deeply and understand the unexpressed meanings projected through them. The register analysis has promoted a reflection of several aspects of identity, a reconnection with cultural variables and the context of situation in which the language is used.

3) Symbolic Festivals and Ceremonies

“What decided him was the conviction of one of his men for the profanation of a masquerade.”
(pg, 42)

“Orimili had witnessed the incident and had been on the point of intervening to rescue the young man from five or six masquerades who converged upon him after he took hold of the cane with which one of them had been threatening him.” (pg, 42)

“In the scuffle one of the masquerades had accidentally knocked off the face-covering of its companion. Immediately there was a cry of outrage and a heavy levy on the unfortunate man”
(pg, 42)

The act of masquerade is situated within the domain of one of the most important festivals in Igbo land connecting members of the society with invoked ancestral spirits. Membership of this group is exclusively reserved for the male genders that are often decked in colorful and elaborate costumes meant to attract attention. Masquerading is an integral part of Igbo ancestral culture which is performed to mark unique seasons and honor ancestral spirits. It is also employed to

entertain the community thereby fostering the chords of love and oneness in society. The name, “masquerade” implies the spirits of the dead, hence the physical representation of spirits through masks. A masquerade performance might be carried out by a team of men consisting of singers, drummers, players and advisers. The context of situation in this discourse reveals the ordeal of a man with the masquerades and the intervening role played by Orimili and how he paid the heavy amount levied on him. Even though this scene is a small portion of the whole text, this act is a representation of a major cultural heritage of the Igbo ancestral uniqueness. Therefore, salient, phonic features were used to depict a graphical representation in the mind of readers and this is significant for re-enacting the Igbo cultural peculiarities in the mind of the readers. It has a purpose to fulfill the meaning of each word about Igbo culture based on linguistic form.

CONCLUSION

This study attempted a register analysis of Igbo cultural significance as represented in Amechi Akwanya’s *Orimili*. Using Halliday’s theory of register (1989), the study observed a number of registers that re-enact Igbo ancestral significance, namely The Ozo Society, Ozo title, Red barrette cap, Eagle feather, Okike, Ogilisi, Agbori, Echiiechi, White, traditional chalk, Ozorite, Ozo feasts, Afor, Masquerading. The selected registers were grouped into different linguistic categories such as Titles and names of character, Ritual ceremony, Status symbols, Symbolic edibles, Symbolic festivals and ceremonies. The study has found out that the field of the selected registers revealed that readers can engage the nature of the social action and activities being carried out within the Igbo context. The social role relationship described by the tenor of discourse projects a high level of affective involvement between the readers and the author while the written mode of discourse is significant for re-enacting Igbo cultural peculiarities in the mind of the readers.

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